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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies: Definition and Guidelines

Deliverable D5.3

Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants

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D5.3. TAIS definition and guidelines [March 2022]

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<i>About RAISD</i>	
<i>Call (part) identifier</i>	<i>H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018</i>
<i>Topic</i>	<i>MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement</i>
<i>Fixed EC Keywords</i>	<i>Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations</i>
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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RAISD Glossary

ARU	Action Research Unit
EC	European Commission
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PRSF	Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum
RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Time-based
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document presents a comprehensive overview of the concept and implementation of the [Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies \(TAIS\)](#) in each RAISD project country.

A [preliminary set of guidelines \(D5.2\)](#) was compiled and submitted on 30 April 2020 that contained information about the planning and tailoring process. The final version of the guidelines (D5.3) contains the detailed analysis of the implemented TAIS pilots only.

RAISD [partners](#) designed and implemented the following TAIS, each of which is presented and analysed in this document:

- In [Spain](#), the TAIS consisted of a training and counselling program for self-employment for Sub-Saharan women seeking international protection, whose application has been accepted, rejected or is pending.
- In [Italy](#), the actual piloting of "ALL you can LEARN" involved Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions, victims of human trafficking currently living in Sicily, originally from various African countries.
- In [Finland](#), the TAIS was designed in the form of two parallel pilot activities. The multilingual online forum's target group were young refugee men with no social connections whereas the other was designed to develop already existing child-care services in the reception centres for families living there.
- In [Hungary](#), the objective of the TAIS was to pilot a trajectory monitoring toolbox for social workers working with refugees to recognise and assess the context of their vulnerability.
- In [Turkey](#), the TAIS focused on the monitoring of social integration of vulnerable refugees through a series of workshops to enhance the capacities and awareness for various stakeholders.
- In [Jordan](#), the TAIS aimed to provide psychological support for refugees together with online trainings about financial, legal and health awareness.
- In [Lebanon](#), the TAIS promoted health awareness among Syrian refugees living in camps. The COVID-19 emergency made it necessary to combine simple awareness-raising activities with a more strategic approach via trainings focusing on social and emotional well-being.

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1. Introduction and disclaimer

This document is an analytical summary of the concept and implementation of the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) in each RAISD project country. The design of these TAISs began in January 2020 and their piloting was supposed to begin in Spring 2020. However, as it will be addressed in detail in this document, the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic made the start of the pilots as planned difficult, if not impossible. Major rearrangements had to be made in all countries that, at some instances, overwrote the previously existing methodological frameworks set for the implementation.

Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants – was in a role of coordination for the TAIS design and implementation, as the leader of the respective Work Package 5, following the general work methodology developed in Work Package 3, leaded by UCM. After an initial training with all partners to understand that methodology, Menedék coordinated the planning process, compiled the preliminary document summarizing TAIS plans – Deliverable 5.2, submitted on 30 April 2020 –, organized a consultation and reporting round for each of the three phases of the pilot implementation, and had a leading role in the collection of final reports and evidence related to the TAIS implementation in each country.

Nonetheless, Menedék did not participate in the process of choosing the actual topic, focus and layout of the TAIS in any of the participating countries except Hungary, and neither did it intervene in the implementation of the TAISs in any way. The decisions about how the TAISs were designed and implemented in each country are therefore the sole responsibility of the respective RAISD consortium members.

This document, Deliverable D5.3 is based primarily on the TAIS Final reports that were submitted by RAISD consortium members by 15 November 2021, using a template developed jointly by UCM, Menedék, UH, CESIE and UNIMED. Besides the information retrieved from these reports, Menedék also reviewed the evidence attached to the reports, i.e. the written or otherwise recorded outputs of the TAIS. These pieces of evidence are available at the RAISD consortium's internal online workspace, on a NextCloud platform. The documentation of the TAIS activities was not entirely accessible for Menedék: some documents were written in local languages other than English, or were stored on platforms that needed specific access permission.

The collected evidence was found satisfactory regarding the TAIS goals and methodologies in almost all cases. In the case of the TAIS pilot implemented in Lebanon, the evidence attached to the reports did not seem to fully underpin neither that they were substantially connected to the issue of reducing the context of vulnerability of specific target groups among the forcibly displaced, nor that the series of trainings and lectures held were really innovative pilot activities, based on accurately collected local evidence.

This points out to difficulties to align the identified vulnerability contexts and their needs with a proper design of tailored practices due to several reasons like the local situation, the available expertise and effort of the teams, or the execution of the collaborative dynamics. Deliverable D3.4 – TAIS methodology and guidelines, authored by UCM, will elaborate on these issues.

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2. The concept of TAIS

2.1. Definition of TAIS

The acronym "TAIS" stands for "Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies". It means implementing innovative, tailored and personalized services designed to respond to the specific needs of one of the vulnerable groups detected after carrying out interviews with vulnerable individuals and working with stakeholders in the framework of the [Action Research Units \(ARU\)](#).

RAISD Grant Agreement Annex 1 - Part B, pp. 5-6. defines the concept of TAIS as follows: "The project hypothesis is that these contextualised strategies will constitute effective ways of dealing with the needs of VGs [vulnerable groups] in FDs [forced displacement situations]. A context will allow identifying whether a practice can be applied in it, and the metrics evaluating if that kind of practice and its results are valuable for the specific actors in that context. The result for this specific objective is therefore the TAISs."

2.2. Actors and timeframe

National teams (Finland, Hungary, Italy, Jordan, Lebanon, Spain, Turkey) included, on one hand, consortium member partners:

- P1 Spain: Complutense University of Madrid (UCM)
- P2 Italy: CESIE
- P4 Finland: University of Helsinki (UH)
- P5 Hungary: Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants (Menedék)
- P6 Turkey: Anadolu University (AU)
- P7 Jordan: Yarmouk University (YU)
- P8 Lebanon: Lebanese International University (LIU)

On the other hand, stakeholders (organizations, specialists, activists, civil society, etc.) in each country took part in the work of the ARU and in developing the TAIS.

The TAIS were open to the participation of all the stakeholders that were working in the ARU together with the consortium members. The degree of involvement in the TAIS may have varied, so the commitment was decided by each organization. Social innovation was a key concept for setting the outlines of stakeholder involvement.

The time assigned for TAIS was around 18 months, with 3 evaluation rounds. In each round consortium members evaluated the evolution of the social intervention project and implemented the necessary improvements according to the problems detected.

The tentative timeframe was set as follows:

- Round 1: 15 April 2020 – 15 November 2020
- Round 2: 15 November 2020 – 15 April 2021
- Round 3: 15 April 2021 – 15 November 2021

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However, national teams could set their own agendas and timelines that differed from these dates.

RAISD Grant Agreement Annex 1 - Part B, pp. 5-6. defines the implementation of TAIS as follows: "In the pilots, the ARUs will implement mainly workshops that include the simulation of TAIS with the stakeholders, and the elicitation of their feedback. These stakeholders must represent all the relevant societal actors, as the objective is to come up with sustainable, yet efficient solutions, where the systemic function goal is a balance between resilience and efficiency. The workshops will be at least one full day activities.

Before the pilots, the ARUs will carry out some preliminary empirical fieldwork to gather information to identify the VCs [vulnerability contexts] they face (SO1) and the attention and inclusion practices they use for them (SO2). In this everyday work, they will create the criteria (SO3) and the mapping (SO4), as tools to match VGs and their needs with suitable practices. When the units implement the recommended practices in the pilots, these will provide feedback to validate the previous results in terms of whether the criteria provided a real assessment of the actors' interests, the practices could be applied in the VC, and the results obtained were those expected. This experience will be used in the development and evaluation of the method."

2.3. Intervention ethics and methodological framework

Implementation of TAIS was based on the following ethical and methodological foundations¹:

- Socio-Ecological Model,
- Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI),
- Action Research Strategy,
- SMART Criteria,
- Actor-Oriented Evaluation.

2.3.1. Socio-Ecological Model

TAIS was conceptualized having in mind the social and political "ecosystem" in which it would take place. Three levels of intervention are distinguished:

- Micro level: individual / interpersonal. Family and affective-emotional context.
- Meso level: institutional. Interactions with communities of origin, receiving communities during transit and at destination, contexts of groups and associations, etc.
- Macro level: policy / law. It is very unlikely that we can achieve results at the macro level during the project.

Macro level was the context to keep in mind all the time. Recommendations could be written aimed at the macro level, but TAIS needed to be implemented on the meso or micro level. If there was an obstacle found on the macro level, which made a given TAIS proposal unfeasible, it had to be modified to something feasible.

Meso level was understood as institutions and organizations, and included entities such as: refugee reception facility, service centre (general for all citizens or refugee-specific facility) and community-based organization (migrant NGO, pro-migrant NGO, relief agency). The types of intervention or change can be in terms of material

¹ Elaborated jointly by UCM and Menedék.

change (improvement of material environment), improved accessibility (information, opening hours, location, language), procedural improvement (new or different services, methodologies) or changes in skills, attitudes and/or knowledge of staff.

Micro level was understood for individuals, including expert staff (service provider), migrants or refugee individuals already in a vulnerability context, migrants or refugee individuals at risk of becoming vulnerable. Here, the types of intervention or change can be in several forms, such as awareness raising and improvement of interpersonal and intercultural skills, prevention of critical situations, rehabilitation restorative interventions, self-help and peer support, or monitoring and improvement of work methodologies.

2.3.2. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

Research needs must arise, first of all, from the social group. TAIS design was not started until the group for which the action research is being carried out would be consulted.

A balance in terms of public vs. private sector, for-profit vs. non-profit sector, ethnicity, gender and local communities needed to be reached, or attempted.

Ethical issues had to be respected throughout the project: gender equality, informed consent, accessibility, respect for diversity, etc.

2.3.3. Action Research Strategy

The anticipation and reflection of innovative action research were expected to enable the TAIS participants to visualize their impact on society and reflect the underlying values and objectives of research in the short, medium and long term.

An action research perspective guaranteed that the project would be flexible, and that it could be adapted to the changes in the needs expressed by participants.

TAIS implementation was aimed to be inclusive, i.e. it had to incorporate the opinions of the stakeholders and of the social group that participated in it; as well as accessible, i.e. all participants should have accessed the planning and implementation process in all its phases.

The concept of vulnerability was assessed for each TAIS, in line with RAISD's Work Package 4.

2.3.4. SMART Criteria

Effective implementation of innovative TAIS was aimed to be based on the following principles: specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, time-based (SMART).

- Specific: it had to be very clear what the TAIS planned to achieve.
- Measurable: the change had to be defined and properly measured.
- Attainable: micro and meso level targets had to be set, in a proportionate manner (so time and money inputs would bring sufficient outputs),

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- Relevant: It had to be related to vulnerability (conceptual relevance) and to existing needs based on the interviews and ARUs (empirical relevance)
- Time-based: A full project cycle had to be planned, and the timeframe had to be realistic/feasible.

2.3.5. Actor-Oriented Evaluation

TAIS evaluation² was based on an actor-oriented definition of indicators.

The indicators for the TAIS were discussed in terms of the following categories:

- Hierarchy: input/output – outcome/result – impact. It was suggested that lower level indicators should be set (input/output).
- Perspective: process-oriented – result-oriented. It was suggested that result-oriented indicators should be given priority.
- Evaluation: baseline, interim, final. It was suggested that baseline and final are a must, interim indicators only if reasonable.

Evaluation activities were undertaken in RAISD's Work Package 7.

2.4. General principles of TAIS design: from evidence to strategy

In line with [RAISD's D3.1. \(Ethics Plan\)](#), compiled by Menedék, TAIS targeting Vulnerable Groups (VGs) of Forcibly Displaced People (FDP), as well as related institutions and societal actors, needed to be consistent with the strict ethical guidelines concerning sensitive data, such as gender, age, ethnicity, health, sexual lifestyle, political opinion, and religious or philosophical conviction (see also part 2.3.2. on Responsible Research and Innovation - RRI). Therefore, all evidence stemming from interviews, ARU meetings and other forms of respondent-driven information exchange, had to be treated with confidentiality. This means that TAIS designs, while they relied on VG and ARU inputs, could only work with anonymized information.

In line with [RAISD D3.2 \(Work methodology & Guidelines\)](#), compiled by UCM, TAIS design relied on the identification of good practices. The consortium worked together in order to define previously existing good practices of inclusion and differentiated attention practices of vulnerable groups of forcibly displaced people in each country. The main points to consider were summarized in D3.2 (p. 47) as follows:

- "Identification of stakeholders that made an identification of the practice;
- Criteria actors or stakeholder are using to assess them as a "good practice";
- Name and leading organization (contact details provided);
- Target VG and type of host community;
- Application setting: context;
- Objectives;
- Length;
- Requirements/ accessibility issues;
- Performance procedures;

² Elaborated jointly by UH and Menedék.

- Difficulties or constrains for its implementation;
- Results;
- Comments."

Information sources for identifying good practices included vulnerable people themselves (through interviews), stakeholders (within the ARU or outside it), and literature review.

Concerning the procedure of working with stakeholder inputs, each ARU discussed existing practices and provided actor-driven criteria to help to conceptualize good practices.

Actor-oriented criteria were defined by D3.2 (p. 48) as follows:

"RAISD is expected to gain a depth knowledge on What does good mean for the different stakeholders that take part in the project according to the quintuple helix.

Therefore, specific works must be developed within each ARU for the identification and discussion of practices:

- Discussing principles, standards, norms, values... What principles, standards, norms, values are named and identify by each type of stakeholder?
- What practices really meet what VGs' needs?
- What and where are the differences?
- What are the common features?"

Criteria compiled through desktop research were also considered. D3.2 (pp. 53-56) lists a total of 28 sources that include examples or criteria of good practices, related to EU institutions, previous EU-funded projects, national or local initiatives. These sources included the Assembly of European Regions, the European Asylum Support Office (EASO), European Migration Network, European Web Site on Integration (EWSI), and a wide range of project documentation material.

Good practices were collected in [D5.1. \(Preliminary catalogue of good attention and inclusion practices\)](#), compiled by LIU. This document also contained a cross-analysis of the national contexts in each country where RAISD consortium members are located. Policies were screened for the following vulnerable groups: children, unaccompanied children, people with disabilities, elderly women, pregnant women, single parents with minor children, LGBTQ groups, and language minorities; as well as concerning human trafficking, health and mental health issues, consequences of torture, rape and other gender violence, other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, and female genital mutilation. Not only the legal background, but the implementation of laws, regulations and policies was analysed, and informal care practices were considered as well. It was also stressed that not only individual (micro level) good practices existed, but the inter-institutional (meso level) network of service providers could also be a field of intervention.

In light of these national contexts, D5.1 collected the information provided by interviewees and ARU members in each country about existing good attention and inclusion strategies that could serve as a model for new practices that could possibly work in the given country context. In the seven countries, a total of 65 good practices were collected and discussed by the respective ARUs.

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TAIS design then followed the framework set by Menedék, in cooperation with UCM and UH (the latter responsible for evaluation in WP7).

The planning process included at least one ARU meeting in each country, where stakeholders could participate in defining the outlines of the TAIS ideas. Menedék, as WP5's leader, provided a continuous support to consortium members. The ideas were summarized in a preliminary version of guidelines, deliverable D5.2, submitted on 30 April 2020.

It has to be noted that the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic caused a considerable backdrop for the process of planning and implementing the TAIS. The pandemic broke out precisely when the implementation of the TAIS should have started, in the spring of 2020. Partners were forced to continue the work from home office, and ARU meetings had to be suspended or transferred (and adapted) to online platforms.

Therefore, all TAIS ideas had to be reconsidered in light of the public health situation and the implemented measures of social distancing. The RAISD consortium decided, at online meetings held on 3 and 9 April 2020, to allow the application of substantial changes to the design of TAIS, in order to be more responsive to the effects of COVID-19.

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3. TAIS design and layout: an overview

3.1. Comprehensive summary of the TAIS

Within the RAISD project, a total of eight TAIS were piloted in the partner countries. The following chapter provides a summary of the activities that were carried out by the national teams (Hungary, Italy, Spain, Finland, Jordan, Turkey and Lebanon) in terms of how the pilot rounds were distributed, on which socio-ecological levels did the TAIS take place, and who were the beneficiaries of the activities.

Each TAIS was tailored to fit the local environment and address the given vulnerability context³ therefore the activities are diverse to respond to the specific needs of the vulnerable individuals.

The TAIS relied on evidence gathered through [interviews with Forcibly Displaced People](#) (FDPs), stakeholder interviews, [Action-Research Units \(ARU\) meetings](#), analysis of previous good practices and desktop research.

- The TAIS in **Spain** consists of a training and counselling program for self-employment for Sub-Saharan women seeking international protection, whose application has been accepted, rejected or is pending.
- In **Italy** the actual piloting of "ALL you can LEARN" involved Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions, victims of human trafficking currently living in Sicily, originally from Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Comoros and Tunisia.
- In **Finland**, the TAIS was designed in the form of two parallel pilot activities. The multilingual online forum's target group was young asylum-seeking men with few social connections with particularly Finnish-speaking men, whereas the other was designed to develop already existing child-care services in the asylum seekers' reception centres for families living there.
- In **Hungary**, the objective of the TAIS was to pilot a trajectory monitoring toolbox for social workers working with refugees to recognise and assess the context of their vulnerability.
- The team in **Turkey** designed the TAIS to focus on the monitoring of social integration of vulnerable FDPs through a series of workshops to enhance the capacities and awareness for various stakeholders.
- In **Jordan**, the TAIS aimed to provide psychological support for refugees together with online trainings about financial, legal and health awareness.
- In **Lebanon**, the TAIS promoted health awareness among Syrian refugees living in camps. The COVID-19 emergency made it necessary to combine simple awareness-raising activities with a more strategic approach via trainings focusing on social and emotional well-being.

The activities took place in *three rounds from spring 2020 until the end of 2021*, each followed by an evaluation process. Adjustments and changes were made according to the results of the evaluation.

The TAIS was designed to take place and affect the different *socio-ecological levels (micro, meso, macro)*, of which the micro and meso levels were assessed to be within the reach of TAIS implementers.

³ For a detailed description of the notion of the "vulnerability context" and its application in the RAISD project, see Deliverable 4.1 - Vulnerability Context: Definition and Guidelines.

- The TAIS in **Spain** attempted, throughout the training and the mentoring program, to improve the autonomy and responsibility of the beneficiaries (micro level), particularly on the economic aspect, avoiding behaviours of dependence on the workers of the entities or third parties. The TAIS was co-designed with public funding organizations as well as private NGOs, therefore embedding the activities in the meso level.
- The **Italian** TAIS was designed to mainly affect FDP environments and vulnerabilities at the micro level. The beneficiaries, through their own personal and professional development process, could indirectly have an impact on the meso level as well.
- In **Finland**, the online forum took primarily place on micro and individual levels. The focus was on individual asylum seekers and voluntary persons and the promotion of the relations between the two groups. However, there was also stress on meso levels in the form of the Finnish Red Cross and the reception system as institutions. The main aim of the second pilot activity was to promote the autonomy and context-specific capabilities of asylum-seeking families, both parents and children. Therefore, the TAIS affected mainly the individual and family levels (micro). Moreover, the TAIS was an intervention to professional and institutional practices in the context of the Finnish reception system (meso).
- In **Hungary**, the TAIS took place on the meso level and potentially affected the micro-level. The emphasis was on the interpersonal and individual conditions of the beneficiaries: for social workers and other helpers, “reviewing” cases, reflecting on them brought professional deepening and the possibility of supervision. Macro-level changes due to the hostile political environment towards asylum-seekers and refugees were impossible for the TAIS to achieve.
- The proposed TAIS of **Turkey** had effects on the micro and meso levels. The trainings had a significant impact on local government and NGO representatives, as well as individuals active in business life.
- In **Jordan**, on the individual level, refugees, identified as VGs among FDPs, benefited from the implemented services tailored to their needs. Also, the implemented services along with the methods, practices and training programs were shared with NGOs and the implemented services potentially affected the country’s policies which assure decent living conditions to them.
- In **Lebanon**, the awareness-raising activities were targeting individuals (micro level) but the strategic approach of the implementation was considering the meso level as well.

The TAIS had *direct and indirect beneficiaries*. Whether a “beneficiary” was a forcibly displaced person, or a person working at an institution or association that provides help or services to the forcibly displaced, depended on the design, layout and context of each TAIS.

- The **Spanish** strategy consisted of developing a training and support process in entrepreneurship so that a group of 14 participating women could access the labour market as self-employment or as employed workers.
- In **Italy**, there were two pilot groups and the TAIS was initially designed for 20 female beneficiaries. In October 2020, activities started with 18 women from Nigeria and Tunisia, yet the ethnic and cultural backgrounds were much diverse. Then in May 2021, activities started with 9 women from mainly Somalia, Comoros Island, Sierra Leone and Nigeria.

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- In the dual strategy of TAIS implementation in **Finland**, the direct beneficiaries were forcibly displaced persons seeking asylum in Finland. Indirect beneficiaries included workers of asylum seekers' reception centres, the Red Cross, and other organizations or individuals working with refugees.
- In **Hungary**, the direct beneficiaries of the TAIS were the service providers. Besides the social workers, psychologists, healthcare workers, legal advisers, ARU members from different refugee-specific organisations, also volunteers who participated in the trainings during the pilot phase benefited from the TAIS.
- In **Turkey**, besides Anadolu University Project Team members, a number of social service personnel, local administration representatives, and social services workers participated in the trainings and benefited from the activities.
- In **Jordan**, the main beneficiaries of the pilot project were the refugees especially the VG regardless the gender, age, and education level. Also, I/NGOs, CBOs, NPOs, and PVOs— which provided psychological services to refugees were also part of the beneficiaries.
- In **Lebanon**, beneficiaries were Syrian refugees who received training and orientation related to healthcare and other current issues.

3.2. Detailed summary of the TAIS

In the following, a detailed overview provides a summary of each TAIS.

3.2.1. TAIS – Spain (UCM)

The aim of the TAIS was to develop competences to promote the socioeconomic inclusion of sub-Saharan refugee women or applicants for international protection in Spain as well as foster the beneficiaries' self-reliance, autonomy and general level of work market competence. The program focused on different skills and capacities (digital, emotional, communication, leadership, management and entrepreneurship) that had been selected to form part of the program, then validated by ARU members and some potential beneficiaries in the consultation processes. These skills also stood out for having a high value for the job market, and the professional and personal development of the beneficiaries. The Spanish TAIS translated into a very flexible social intervention process, highly adaptable to the needs and demands of the participants and the COVID-19 context. The participating women were highly engaged and formed an active group in the design, development, and evaluation of the practices. The TAIS was a training and support process with a twofold course of action: In terms of entrepreneurship and strengthening of abilities and competences.

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/#spain>

3.2.2. TAIS – Italy (CESIE)

The ultimate aim of the TAIS was to increase learners' decision-making capacity as they are to be intended as "co-experts" of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) based inclusion strategy, thus having the opportunity to decide and co-design their learning experience according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics and time availability, etc.). Expected results of the Italian TAIS included the increased highly vulnerable and

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forcibly displaced female participation in Education and Training; decreased initial resistance and attendance reluctance; reduced in-training dropout rates among FDP women. In order to achieve these goals, the excessive strictness of learning paths and hours of commitment were avoided and replaced by a flexible learning environment. The actual piloting of "ALL you can LEARN" involved Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions, victims of human trafficking currently living in Sicily, originally from Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Comoros and Tunisia.

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/#italy>

3.2.3. TAIS I – Finland (UH)

A voluntary group of young asylum-seeking men were invited to join, together with Finnish-speaking voluntary young men, in an online thread to discuss the experiences of asylum seekers and everyday life in Finnish society. The aim was to promote the learning of both asylum seekers and voluntaries. The former group learned the language, Finnish culture from the perspective of ordinary men and received more information about various possibilities in Finland. As for the latter group, voluntary men were able to have first-hand knowledge about the lives of asylum seekers in Finland and about their home countries. Further, both groups developed their skills in online communications. The online discussions were moderated and, when necessary, translated from languages used by asylum seekers into Finnish. Moreover, two asylum-seeking peer moderators were recruited during the second and third piloting rounds to instigate discussions and, when necessary, to help in translating the messages. Each forum lasted approximately five weeks.

3.2.4. TAIS II – Finland (UH)

The TAIS aimed to develop child-care services in reception centres in Finland. To promote the wellbeing of asylum-seeking families with small children, child-care activities were developed together with the Finnish Red Cross (FRC) reception centres. The general state of child-care services in FRC reception centres was surveyed and two reception centres providing comparatively wide-ranging child-care services were involved to develop their activities further. Child-care activities of the two centres were observed and parents and professionals involved were interviewed. The knowledge acquired was used to qualitatively improve the content of the child-care activities. Moreover, a trial of more regular child-care services was carried out in one reception centre. As a result, a model for child-care services for reception centres was aimed to be established to be used for all reception centres throughout Finland. In addition, the knowledge collected in the TAIS was used to argue the importance of asylum-seeking children's access to municipal early childhood education and care services.

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/#finland>

3.2.5. TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS was to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures. Social workers and service providers analysed individual cases in order to build a "Trajectory monitoring toolbox" of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. The toolbox was built around evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" and the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and reduce the isolation of vulnerable

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individuals. Social workers and service providers in Hungary should be informed about who, where, and how to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. The toolbox had the primary objective to recognise and assess a context of vulnerability. Based on its content, institutions and organisations can improve their internal workflow, as well as for inter-institutional cooperation, to make trajectories less demanding and vulnerability reduction more effective. The toolbox contains two major elements: a Handbook and a Self-reflection tool.

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/#hungary>

3.2.6. TAIS – Turkey (AU)

The TAIS implemented in Turkey aimed to develop the service providers capacity to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges (especially experienced while accessing the daily life practices) of forcibly displaced women and girls. This TAIS was implemented in two main stages. In the first stage, the AU team conducted an assessment of service providers working with vulnerable groups on behalf of the government. Service providers should know the need- and rights-based approaches and advocacy issues when working with vulnerable groups. Inclusion, diversity, and monitoring training were provided for service providers' capacity development. The trainings aimed to provide basic information and measure the knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Pre-test and post-test methods were used to measure the impact of each training. The second stage was assessing the capacity of service providers to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges.

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/#turkey>

3.2.7. TAIS – Jordan (YU)

In Jordan a Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) has been developed to spread awareness about asylum seekers psychological and social support, reflecting the social responsibility for supporting the needs of asylum seekers in terms of mental health and psychological aid. The main goal of this program was to enable asylum seekers to be self-reliant, independent, and with little or no need for external support. To achieve such a goal, asylum seekers had to convert their negative experiences into a motivation that support their future life. Early identification of psychological distress and trauma, and effective care were essential in discovering the strengths that asylum seekers could rely on to face their daily challenges and benefit from existing opportunities. PRSF was designed to deliver various services that contribute to minimizing the effects of psychological and social challenges. These services included psychological services, social support, family services, healthcare access, economic support, and legislative support. They would contribute to improving the asylum seekers' lifestyle and enable them to integrate into the host community.

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/#jordan>

3.2.8. TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)

In Lebanon, the designed TAIS addressed social, emotional, and academic problems. The programme had a positive impact on the Syrian people living in camps. It delivered a holistic coronavirus awareness to children, pregnant women, the elderly, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immune-compromised. The TAIS aimed to deliver an online awareness campaign called Health 4 SEAD "Health, Social-Emotional, Academic,

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Development". The outcome of this pilot project aimed at empowering a strong pool of NGOs and Information Focal Point networks all over Lebanon in preparing them to facilitate and support their teaching efforts of displaced people in refugee camps. This was done through the LIU Health Committee's active participation and sharing of practical experiences utilising online means. Essentially, the programme centred around a plethora of different skills and capacities (digital, emotional, communication, leadership, management, and English language) that were chosen to be a constituent of the programme.

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/innovation/tais/#lebanon>

4. Analysis of the context of TAIS: from vulnerability to tailored attention

This chapter presents and analyzes the broader and specific relations between the different Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) and the vulnerability context definition. In this regard, we are using the synthetic *vulnerability context definition* outlined in Delivery [D4.1 Vulnerability context: definition and guidelines – preliminary version](#), and we supplement it with another potential classification, the spectrum of *dynamic and static vulnerability contexts*. Finally, to achieve a more comprehensive picture, we will reflect on the *vulnerability levels* where the country-specific TAIS were applied.

Before analyzing the TAIS activities through these lenses, it is essential to mention the formation briefly from the original designs to the implemented versions.

4.1. The road to TAIS designs

The common starting point of the partners' Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies is the findings of the field research and the inputs of the Action Research Units (ARU). Both shaped the final vulnerability context definition identified the country-specific problems and the potential areas of the TAIS.

At the same time, it is a clearly visible pattern – that comes from the nature of the project – that the ARU's professional inputs had a significantly stronger impact on TAIS activities. The fieldwork (i.e., structured individual interviews with members of vulnerable groups and professionals) provided a perspective to analyze vulnerability like a general context. However, this research strongly shaped the concept of vulnerability context, and it helped to describe and define the phenomenon; the TAIS activities targeted more specific issues that are not necessarily the core elements of the research data. The final pilot project objectives derive primarily from the ARU. Then the final forms were shaped by key practicalities such as feasibility, sustainability, project budget, actual political environment, and COVID-19.

Furthermore, all TAIS designs had to adapt to rapid changes in country-specific contexts during the implementation period. As a result, not all the initially identified pilot objectives could be tackled entirely in some cases. Here are three examples to illustrate this process and its different extent.

For example, Menedék Association's ARU highlighted the need to strengthen the general level of trust in the service provider network in order to have a more effective system to deal with vulnerable groups. Nevertheless, COVID-19 restrictions have not allowed organizing the necessary community-building activities.

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In other cases, new entry points and implementation plans were needed to use the initially developed tools and strategies to tackle the main vulnerability context in the TAIS. For example, CESIE, due to different reasons, was facing low engagement of VG members. Therefore, to access the VGs and cover their initial pilot questions, CESIE's team moved the activities to new locations and restarted the activities directly within the centers where the vulnerable women find shelter.

Adaptation was not always possible to the contextual changes. For example, Lebanese International University (LIU) started to design a pilot project on education access of highly vulnerable Syrian FDPs. However, as the country's political, security, economic, and health system collapsed (at the time of the planned TAIS implementation period), the pilot shifted towards emergency intervention.

Regardless of the extreme change of the circumstances and what the RAISD teams were able to implement, it is still possible to apply one comprehensive analytical framework to demonstrate the TAIS activities from the aspect of *vulnerability*. However, to proceed, it is necessary to introduce these framework cornerstones.

4.2. Vulnerability in a theoretical perspective

The work undertaken in RAISD's WP4 explores the concept of vulnerability context and its theoretical background (see [Deliverable D4.2](#), page 33-34). To understand the relation between the different Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies and the theoretical background, we summarize this angle.

At the beginning of the RAISD project, country teams carried out field research based on interviews with individuals who had (or potentially had) first-hand experience about vulnerabilities of FDP living in the context of receiving countries. One hundred seventy-eight interviews with forcibly displaced people were conducted, with 25 interviewees from each participating country: Spain, Italy, Turkey, Hungary, Lebanon, Finland, and Jordan. 60% of the total samples were women (107) and 40% men (71).

The objective was to understand the different layers and patterns of vulnerability contexts.

Vulnerability is a multi-dimensional, differential, scale-dependent, and dynamic concept that, in any context, has an accumulative nature. While describing vulnerability, factors such as age, gender, religion, culture, education, job opportunities, and access to fundamental rights should be taken into consideration. In this context, the conditions of each individual and the conditions of the host country are effective in defining vulnerability.

Vulnerability emerges based on someone's personal condition in a given context. Therefore, vulnerability is not an endowment or personal quality. It is a personal status that may result in vulnerability activated by the given context. Contexts are fluid elements that require analysis from the perspective of the actual person.

Based on our approach so far, we see vulnerability as a matrix of three main elements:

- The first is how the individual appears in the matrix.
- The second is the context, the different levels of the individual's environment.

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- The third is the area where the individual consciously or subconsciously experiences the danger, damage, or vulnerability caused by the interconnected individual conditions and contexts. These main areas are the primary needs, fundamental human rights, and identity.

We will use this matrix to see the vulnerability contexts that the different Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies are targeting.

4.3. Vulnerability from a practical TAIS implementation perspective

The TAIS implementations themselves provided the RAISD team with a new perspective on understanding the nature of vulnerability from the project planning angle. The plans of the pilot interventions all had to deal with a question of "in what vulnerability contexts are we able to facilitate change in the given conditions." So, from this feasibility perspective arose the need to look at the matrix with a new approach and create another classification of vulnerability context. In the cases of the RAISD project, it is possible to use the following – less theoretical but more practical – dichotomy.

This dichotomy is not the two sides of the coin. Instead, it is more likely the two ends of a spectrum:

- A (rather) Dynamic vulnerability element. The main characteristic is its ability to change regardless of the available resources.

Examples: housing questions, labor market integration issues, communication limitations, obstacles to services, emergency cases, coping strategies, education

- A (rather) Static vulnerability element. The main characteristic is its difficulty (or impossibility) to change.

Examples: The individual's broader macro environment. Hostile political and social circumstances, lack of services. How the individual appears in the matrix: nature or characteristics (e.g., shyness). The condition or circumstance (e.g., unaccompanied minor, traumatized, single parent). Pre-migration resources (human, social, economic, and cultural capital). Individual socio-demographic profile.

Service providers, researchers, policymakers may consider this circle of questions. Besides looking at vulnerability context primarily from the viewpoint of the vulnerable group, it is essential to analyze it with the dynamic-static spectrum in mind.

4.4. Levels where a vulnerability context appears

The third potential frame to systematically interpret vulnerability contexts is the levels where they appear and originated. The RAISD project, from its early design, differentiates between micro, meso, and macro levels as "places" where vulnerability contexts are created and as "places" where pilot Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies may have an impact.

The micro-level is the sphere where individual conditions mark vulnerability. The following questions quoted from Deliverable D4.2, page 37, define the nature of this level:

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“Do the refugees have a family with them? How does loneliness play a role in shaping an individual’s vulnerability? How is mental and physical health regarded? Is the family’s income sufficient to cover mental and physical healthcare services that the national healthcare system does not provide for free? Does income affect the education of minors in the household? How is child labor regarded? What personal characteristics or traits might make refugees more vulnerable to crime?”

Meso level is defined to include: interactions with origin communities, reception communities during the transit and in destination, group contexts as well as organizations (social capital and support), roles of formal social institutions (mediation institutions): education system; job market; religious authorities; mass media; judicial sphere; security (e.g., border agreements),

A significant characteristic is that the meso level functions as a bridge between the macro and micro levels and assumes the role of the enforcer of laws and regulations taking place at the macro level.

The macro-level vulnerability affects the whole society or some specific groups. Individuals are the units that make up a society, and they are affected by a situation that impacts society in general. Macro-level elements are religion, ideology, social structure, politics, domestic law, and international agreements. The power of the vulnerable groups to influence these situations is very low or equal to zero. All written and unwritten norms in a society can be included at the macro level. For example, if the opinions of individuals do not match the general opinion of the society they live in, they may be exposed to exclusion and discrimination.

As it is highlighted, vulnerability contexts are complex and multi-dimensional. Analyzing the dimensions, one may identify potential intervention points in all the levels. For example, destitution can generate a highly vulnerability context, and with a domino effect, it creates other cumulative vulnerable situations in the individual's life.

Suppose unemployment is the possible cause of destitution. We have to analyze the level (micro, meso, macro) from where unemployment is originated. The person's lack of skills is a micro-level vulnerability. Obstacles in the employer's internal system are a meso level vulnerability. Alternatively, lack of access to the labor market because of the legal status is described as a macro-level vulnerability. Indeed, this example shows as well that all the three vulnerability levels can play a role at the very same time. In most cases, the roots of the vulnerability context are from two or three levels simultaneously. However, there are cases, but it is rarer that a vulnerability element can be simplified to one area.

4.5. Relation between different TAIS implementation experiences and vulnerability contexts

Based on the outlined framework, we apply the following systematic questions to build a comprehensive understanding of the TAIS activities:

- What is the vulnerable group that TAIS was designed for?
- What was the targeted theoretical vulnerability context?
- What is the classification of the TAIS on the dynamic-specific spectrum of vulnerability context?
- What kind of action was implemented?
- In which level(s) did the TAIS action appear?

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- What are the direct and indirect results of the action from a vulnerability perspective?

4.5.1. TAIS – Spain (UCM)

The RAISD team of Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM) arguably carried out the most extensive TAIS preparation. After conducting interviews with experts and vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced and organizing seven meetings with 36 different organizations, they concluded that one of the most vulnerable groups in Spain is the one formed by Sub-Saharan women. Barriers and obstacles in employability are among the primary elements of their vulnerability context, often with additional difficulties due to family ties, cultural and linguistic differences and racist attitudes among part of the local population and political parties. Therefore, the Spanish TAIS was piloting a Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program. It aimed to develop personal skills and competencies closer to the dynamic end of the spectrum. At the same time, static elements were taken into consideration, such as fostering the beneficiaries' self-reliance, autonomy, and general level of work market competence.

The Spanish TAIS focused on building and implementing a training program on different digital, emotional, communication, leadership, management, and entrepreneurship skills and capacities. Sub-Saharan women were the direct beneficiaries of the activity. The experience of the preparation and implementation process had significant impacts on the ARU and involved the NGO sector.

4.5.2. TAIS – Italy (CESIE)

CESIE in Italy designed the TAIS activity for a specific group of highly vulnerable forcibly displaced women. The context is the low access and participation (high dropout rate) in educational programs of women facing exploitation and victims of human trafficking. Many of the vulnerability contexts in this field are static, such as family status or earlier trauma. The TAIS aims to positively impact with dynamic elements at personal level (increased self-awareness and decision-making capacity) and at educational level (decreased early dropout rates). A set of experiential training was piloted. The training experience was implemented over 16 sessions/40 hours in summer 2021, covering orientation sessions (understanding learning objectives to be achieved); actual face-to-face training sessions, based on twenty learning objectives selected by each participant (Knowledge areas to choose from: Active citizenship and democracy; Digitalisation; Life Skills; Health and wellbeing; Social cohesion, equity and equality; Inclusive societies and cultures; Employment and work); local study visits as an opportunity for debate, exchange and mutual learning and final evaluation and capitalization sessions. The direct impact of the pilot was the strongest in the micro-level of the participating women.

Moreover, as outlined in CESIE's TAIS report, there was an indirect but significant impact in the meso level. The combined actions further improved and expanded the dialogue between institutions, bodies, associations, and grassroots who have been working together for years to construct inclusive processes for highly vulnerable groups in Palermo. During the pilot experience itself, important direct and indirect synergies were created at the local level with other institutions and centers that support the wellbeing, education, and autonomy of trafficked women.

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4.5.3. TAIS I – Finland (UH)

The University of Helsinki designed two TAIS activities in separate fields. The first one reflected on the vulnerabilities of young asylum-seeking men. They are rarely considered to suffer from vulnerabilities even though they constitute a highly discriminated group in Finland, and few services are targeted to them. This vulnerability context and the language-related social isolation were the target which the Finnish sub-project aimed to challenge. In an online thread, young asylum-seeking men and Finnish-speaking voluntary young men were invited to share their experiences of everyday life in the Finnish society. The aim on the micro-level was to promote the learning of both asylum seekers and volunteers.

4.5.4. TAIS II – Finland (UH)

The second TAIS of the University of Helsinki described a complex vulnerability context and a relatively simple tailored attention and inclusion strategy. In Finland, asylum-seeking families do not have the right to early childhood education in municipal day-care centers before the pre-school at the age of six. Moreover, reception centers are not obligated to provide child-care, and the level of child-care services varies significantly between different reception centers. This vulnerability context has repercussions on both parental and child wellbeing: parents cannot focus on their wellbeing and settlement, and their children are segregated from Finnish-speaking peers and miss structured activities supporting their learning and development. As an apparent reaction to this situation UH TAIS team aimed to develop child-care services in reception centers in Finland. This issue and the impact of the pilot appear at the micro level of vulnerable groups (asylum-seeking families), but it is relevant at the meso level as service development and at the macro level as potential advocacy activity targeting policymakers. Similar to the domino effect of lack of child-care solutions, providing child-care might have broad and indirect positive impacts.

4.5.5. TAIS – Hungary

Menedék Association continued the field research during the first period of the TAIS. The Hungarian RAISD team aimed to analyze the perspective of the professional service providers (social workers, psychologists, legal advisors, volunteer helpers) on vulnerability context in their direct work and engagement with refugees. In this TAIS, the activity field was not a well-described vulnerable group but a potentially vulnerable situation when a refugee uses a helping service. Misinformation, misunderstanding, incompetency, and the attitude itself of the professional helper may create a vulnerability context. Knowledge, preparedness, and self-reflection may prevent or deepen vulnerability contexts. The research activity involving intensively the practitioners showed that self-reflection is an essential tool in dealing with highly vulnerable groups. Menedék Association developed a pilot project in the meso level of self-reflection activities and a training handbook where the research results on vulnerability context and the experience of vulnerable refugees are transformed into suitable learning material.

4.5.6. TAIS – Turkey (AU)

Anadolu University team concluded from their field research and ARU discussions that the most exposed group are maternal women of the Syrian refugee community. The vulnerability context arose from women being

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exposed to different types of violence that are among other issues linked to language barriers, cultural differences, and dysfunctional information mechanisms. In this broad field, the Anadolu team decided to support service providers to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges (especially regarding the challenges experienced while accessing daily life practices) of forcibly displaced women and girls. So, they have detected the primarily macro-level vulnerability and built a pilot to indicate changes in its meso level environment. The mentioned vulnerability context is extremely complex and hence static. The chosen meso level for the pilot intervention is a specific segment that is more dynamic. Inclusion, diversity, and monitoring training have been offered to service providers. The training aimed to provide basic information to service on inclusion, diversity, and monitoring issues and to measure their knowledge, skills, and attitudes in these matters. The report by the Anadolu team does not elaborate on whether the training material was specially designed to deal with the earlier identified vulnerable group of Syrian maternal women and girls.

4.5.7. TAIS – Jordan (YU)

The Jordanian RAISD team from Yarmouk University focused on the vulnerable group of refugees and asylum-seeking people who suffer from mental health issues. The limited access to psychological aid and the related social stigmas creates vulnerability contexts. It appears in different formats but at all levels (micro, meso, macro). The Jordanian TAIS deals with the context on the personal (micro) level by facilitating direct service opportunities and by related training packages building the capacity of service providers (on the meso level). As a direct pilot intervention, PRSF has been designed to deliver various services that minimize the effects of psychological and social challenges. These services cover the rather dynamic sides of the mentioned vulnerability context, including psychological services, social support, family services, healthcare access, economic support, and legislative support.

4.5.8. TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)

The RAISD team of Lebanese International University had to redesign the TAIS plans due to the extreme turbulences in the political and social environment, plus the COVID-19 circumstances. They built an awareness-raising campaign called *Health, Social-Emotional, Academic, Development*. Despite the Lebanese team identifying the elderly, maternal women, and young infants as the riskiest group among vulnerable groups (according to their report), they have not specified the TAIS to these vulnerable groups. The general vulnerability context is the hardship of accessing essential health services in tandem with the problem of accessing information mechanisms about COVID-19 related topics. LIU delivered a holistic online coronavirus awareness-raising campaign. The need for such an outreach activity is evident, especially in the case of highly vulnerable groups. However, the project is hardly interpretable from a piloting aspect, and LIU's TAIS report, we could not detect development and research ambitions. Due to its limitations, such an online information campaign can only target the most dynamic vulnerability context – the lack of information at the micro-level.

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5. The COVID-19 effect: an overview of the adjustments

5.1. Comprehensive summary of the challenges caused by COVID-19 and the adjustments of TAIS implementation

The COVID-19 pandemic broke out precisely when the implementation of the TAIS should have started, in the spring of 2020. The immediate effect of the emergency situation was a lockdown that made personal meetings, workshops, courses etc. unfeasible. It became obvious that – while many of the activities could be continued and carried out online – forcibly displaced people living in a context of vulnerability have limited means to attend online activities.

At the time of submitting the preliminary version of TAIS guidelines (D5.2, 30 April 2020), it was not sure how the public health situation would change in late 2020 and 2021 in the participating countries. The preliminary guidelines therefore contained TAIS plans which were, to some extent, either delayed, or revisited during the second half of 2020 in order to better fit to a changed reality. The implementation took into account the steps of the original planning process, as well as the ethical and methodological standards of the project – however, it had to be adapted to a different socio-ecological context than in which it was planned.

Nonetheless, the increased need for protecting vulnerable individuals in light of the COVID-19 pandemic made these changes necessary, and the implementation of the project activities yielded the promise that they would become a very good way for directly assessing new challenges through coordinated action.

In the following, a short overview of challenges and adjustments related to COVID-19 is presented for each implementing country, based on the report of the project partner institutions.

5.2. Detailed summary of the challenges caused by COVID-19 and the adjustments of TAIS implementation

5.2.1. TAIS – Spain (UCM)

In Spain, total lockdown began in March 2020 and the state of alarm was extended to the end of June. Due to that, the UCM team experienced an absolute impossibility to work with the target groups and to hold face-to-face meetings. At the beginning of the lockdown, the UCM team considered the option of remote meetings and consultations. However, the emergency work of the entities of the ARU, as well as the lack of technological resources and computer skills of vulnerable groups impeded the UCM team from adopting immediate online measures for the co-creation of TAIS. The pandemic severely hit and is still affecting several vulnerable groups, but especially economic and forced migrants with fewer support networks. Finally, after some adaptations and when the NGOs become more available, the TAIS was designed and validated with ARU members and final beneficiaries through online and remote meetings and calls.

The ARU decided to carry out an online training. To allow the women to participate in the training, a tablet with an internet connection was given to each of them. In a context of total isolation, especially in the case of these migrant women, the TAIS also favoured social and emotional contact among peers.

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The health crisis brought about an economic crisis that forced many small businesses to close. Due to the difficulty of starting a new business in this context, the UCM team decided to adapt the TAIS and to add a mentoring program not only for entrepreneurship, but also to prosper in the labour market.

After the total lockdown, a series of urgent prevention measures were adopted at the regional level, many of them affecting the freedom of movement in different neighbourhoods of Madrid. After the first months of the TAIS implementation, the UCM team observed that many TAIS beneficiaries had difficulties engaging in the training programme. Therefore, when possible, some face-to-face sessions were held, complying with all the protocols and without putting TAIS beneficiaries at risk.

From the linguistic perspective of these women who are not fluent in Spanish, online training increased the lack of understanding. This was solved with in-person support from the UCM team, attending one by one the beneficiaries who presented the most difficulties.

5.2.2. TAIS – Italy (CESIE)

The co-authored design process of TAIS had started about when the first COVID-19 lockdown came into force (March–May 2020). Activities with piloting group 1 (18 participants) came to a stop during the new COVID-19 outbreak with strict social encounter limitations with adjustment to video sessions (November 2020–January 2021). Activities with piloting group 2 (9 participants) could be finalized by reducing the number of in-presence training hours (April–September 2021).

COVID-19 affected consistently the hosting of trainees at CESIE's training facilities (group 1) and the piloting within the CAS centres where trainees were living with their children (group 2).

The impact of COVID-19 and regulations meant that meetings with piloting group 1 were no longer face-to-face but at a distance. The first piloting participants were consulted individually if they agreed to switch to online modalities and if they would have available a digital device and internet connection to be able to continue with the activities, at least for the first part of the orientation sessions. The majority agreed, but actual results showed that the women did not have the necessary skills to use digital tools for distance education and the equipment used (smartphones mainly) was not adequate; therefore, the piloting of group 1 came to a hold in December 2021.

Online support measures have been integrated to help learners in transitioning to distance learning, in Italian and in English, in seven different thematic areas: 1. Active citizenship and democracy, 2. Digitalisation, 3. Life Skills, 4. Health and wellbeing, 5. Social cohesion, equity and equality, 6. Inclusive societies and cultures, 7. Employment and work.

Despite the above challenges, a positive unexpected result of the COVID-19 period was that, due to a forced increase of distance learning methods and approaches targeting pupils and trainees, ARU members found professionals in education unprepared with the digital delivery modes and knowledge multiplication – therefore, it was a specific stakeholder request to offer a Resource Database for ARU members and the wider educational knowledge communities (Community of Users), where to seek guidance, training and teaching material with focus on topics related to migration and various inclusive methodologies for different types of

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HVG and degrees of vulnerability. These resources were integrated to the platform <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach/>.

5.2.3. TAIS I – Finland (UH)

In Finland, mobilities of forcibly displaced people have been reduced to a minimum. Only a few asylum seekers had been able to arrive in Finland due to several restrictions in European immigration policies. In 2020 and 2021, Finnish reception centres have been inhabited by asylum seekers who suffer from protracted waiting in uncertainty. This was manifested in reduced mental health, unwillingness to participate in offered activities and despair. Consequently, at the time when TAIS implementers were trying to recruit participants in a novel and inclusive trial, reception centres were inhabited by a reduced number of asylum seekers lacking motivation. Also, as a result of decreasing number of asylum seekers, several reception centres were closed, which hampered the willingness and eagerness of reception centre workers to invest time in extra tasks such as co-operating with external projects.

Social distancing rules made it impossible to UH staff members to meet reception centre professionals and get to know them in the level that would have increased their understanding of the TAIS and the ideas behind it. While for TAIS I, the online forum did not require face-to-face activities, they would have been beneficial in trust building and in recruitment. Also, due to restrictive measures, reception centre professionals were not able to meet asylum seekers in person to let them know about the possibility of participating in the forum.

5.2.4. TAIS II – Finland (UH)

Concerning Finland's TAIS II, social distancing policies affected both provision of child-care services and UH staff members' physical access to reception centres. Because of the restrictive measures, the whole first cycle was implemented from distance by conducting remote interviews with asylum-seeking parents and e-surveying reception centre professionals. In one involved centre (A), child club activities were replaced by home-delivered activity bundles that included games, toys and crafting materials with instructions. In the second cycle in autumn 2020, a planned visit to this centre to observe these alternative activities was cancelled due to a worsening pandemic situation. Information was, therefore, gathered by video-interview with the centre's professionals.

As mobilities of forcibly displaced people have been reduced to a minimum, the trial of more intensive child-care services in the third round of implementation had the obstacle of not having families with small children in one of the centres (A). The trial was implemented in one centre (B) only.

The solutions for data gathering in the time of social distancing (video and phone interviews and an e-survey) were able to produce certain kind of information from the services. However, more ethnographic observation while being physically present was needed in order to create a coherent picture of the services. Visits were carried out in the second and third rounds in the centre B. While the withdrawal of the centre A was a regrettable turn, UH staff members were able to invest more for the trial of the remaining centre B.

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5.2.5. TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)

In order to assure the safety of TAIS participants, some adjustments were made in the preparation.

The activities and the meetings were developed online, and Menedék Association switched to remote working. So did other ARU members. These changes, however, did not have negative effects on the TAIS implementation. Furthermore, social workers participated in a needs/skills assessment and an online capacity building training that helped them to work with vulnerable individuals using new methods (including online communication channels).

On some occasions, however, it was challenging to organise the ARU meetings and focus groups in the online space, but at the same time, it also provided new possibilities. Organising the meetings online allowed the participation of those ARU and focus group members who do not live in Budapest to participate.

As described in the previous point, a final element was planned to be added to the TAIS, namely, a multi-day workshop fostering inter-organizational cooperation among stakeholders working with refugees. Given the security concerns related to the COVID-19 pandemic, this element was not implemented. Further ARU meetings in 2022 will serve as a platform for the activities planned as part of the TAIS.

5.2.6. TAIS – Turkey (AU)

COVID-19 conditions and the variability of government decisions and the uncertainty created by this situation caused difficulties in the selection of the platform where the trainings within the scope of TAIS would be held. This situation also caused the postponement of the dates of the trainings. In addition, the target audience's lack of technical proficiency in using digital platforms has hindered the delivery of all trainings remotely.

In order to solve this situation, the necessity of integrating online and face-to-face platforms emerged, and it was deemed appropriate to implement pilot trainings in order to ensure the mentioned integration and eliminate possible problems. As a result of the pilot trainings, a mixed online and face-to-face method was applied, and the trainings were carried out in this way by taking the necessary health precautions.

Meeting halls were regularly disinfected before each training and ARU meetings. Furthermore, participants were expected to provide their HES Code (a number indicating the status of the individual regarding COVID-19) and vaccination cards in order to be able to participate in the trainings. Participants who were not vaccinated or not able to show proof of vaccination at the date trainings were held, were expected to provide their PCR test results they obtained within the last 48 hours.

5.2.7. TAIS – Jordan (YU)

Jordan was the first country in the region to respond to the crisis, by imposing a curfew, and closing all educational institutions across the Kingdom, which made it one of the countries that succeeded in relatively controlling the numbers of injuries and deaths in that period.

During the pandemic, refugees living in Jordan experienced many psychological stimuli accompanying anxiety, stress, depression, and many psychological effects that needed immediate psychological support. In light of

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the emerging COVID-19 crisis, refugees faced a set of changes without preparation, such as having to isolate from the outside world due to the imposition of domestic isolation, and the loss of their temporary work that used to meet their personal and material needs. It could have many severe psychological effects related to their mental and physical health.

As a result of the repeated closures in that period and the prevention of gatherings, meetings were held via the Zoom program, in addition to holding meetings of no more than 20 people, and this led to an increase in the burden and preparations. Data collection from refugees was done through an electronic link designed, and sent via WhatsApp, phone call and their e-mail. There were difficulties and restrictions in holding workshops, especially with the allowed number, size of the room where the workshop was held and the ability of the refugees to attend due to shut down of public transportation.

5.2.8. TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)

In Lebanon, the COVID-19 crisis unfolded together with other political, social and economic crises that were exacerbated further by the catastrophic Beirut Port explosion. This constituted an unforeseen risk factor that was to impact the direction of the study and the adjustments that were made to move the research process forward. In the aftermath of the Beirut disaster, Lebanon declared a state of emergency, and a series of lockdowns and curfews were put in place to control the spread of the virus. The effects of these measures were devastating, with many closing shops, experiencing income cuts, or job losses.

In light of the extraordinary situation, the LIU team decided – in accordance with the coordinating partner of the RAISD project and the leaders of the WPs – to move from face-to-face interviews to remote surveys, and conduct interviews with representatives of NGO's or institutions that had previously worked with refugees and VGs in the respective study areas.

Consultations and interviews with refugees and VGs were conducted to involve them in defining the focus of the project. Despite the delays, interviews and survey results indicated that most of the students at LIU expressed interest in participating in the research and to discuss issues that were relevant to them and made their voices heard by stakeholders and decision-makers. Their participation in the research was an empowering experience that helped them to overcome the pain and trauma as refugees and VGs in the host country. Indeed, many of those interviewed felt valued, coped with sadness and grief, and made a change in their lives. However, some interview participants had dissident views and were disappointed regarding the impact the research will have on decision-making and on improving their situations as refugees and VGs.

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6. Successes and failures: lessons learnt from piloting

The question of success and failure is an essential one when assessing the TAIS. As the TAIS are pilot interventions, limited in their scope and time, this context should be taken into account when assessing their success. The following section provides an overview of the various criteria along which the RAISD Consortium Partners reported on the perceived successes and failures of their respective TAIS.

6.1. Analytical criteria for assessing the TAIS

The analysis below is not an actual assessment and evaluation of each intervention, rather a content analysis of the responses given by the project partners, focusing on the various interpretative frameworks in which success and failure are discussed and their interpretation is constructed.

The following analytical criteria were used:

- *Agency and ownership:* who speaks, whose success/failure it is. Service providers and beneficiaries are two entities that were asked about directly in the reporting template, however the balance and dynamic relationship between the two, as well as references to other stakeholders (the research/coordinator team, the ARU, professional partners etc.) are indicative.
- *The location of the issue:* where does the success/failure emerge – internal or external factors. Sometimes it is difficult to differentiate between the two, and some TAIS refer to a dynamic relationship between the two types.
- *The nature/type of the success/failure:* process-related, output/outcome-related, result or even impact-related. These areas shall be discussed in more details in the separate report on evaluation, however we find it important to see what the main issues that can be generalised as patterns for success and failure.

In the following we give a short summary of the successes and failures of each TAIS. This analysis is not a detailed and descriptive presentation of the content of the individual TAIS reports, for more details therefore one needs to consult those individual documents separately.

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6.2. Detailed summary of successes

6.2.1. TAIS – Spain (UCM)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: A balanced triangle: service providers, beneficiaries, and the coordination team. The focus of the success is the perceived positive change in the situation and characteristics of the beneficiaries. There is no discrepancy between the assessments given by the three groups.

The location of the issue: Both internal and external: gender awareness, and appropriate gender composition of the service providers; flexibility and adaptability to beneficiaries' needs and expectations; good cooperation with external partners; attention and support from the ARU. *“Our ARU was definitely one of the success factors of the Spanish TAIS.”*

The nature/type of the success:

Rather result oriented: beneficiaries' skills development, opening-up, self-realisation – even outside of the TAIS. *“I become aware I can, I am able to do things.”*

6.2.2. TAIS – Italy (CESIE)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Mostly centred around beneficiaries, less emphasis on service providers, however partner institutions and their personnel appear as those who benefitted from and contributed to the project's success. Empowerment and competence development is the success in case of beneficiaries, accessibility, acceptability and relevance (validity) is the success in case of the service providers (and their partners).

The location of the issue: Most success factors are internal ones, related to the design and content of the service. Good inter-agency cooperation and the location of the service can be considered as external ones.

The nature/type of the success: Partly process oriented: access, retention, cooperation and interaction with beneficiaries and stakeholders. Partly output/outcome related: competence development of beneficiaries, immediate change in attitudes and communication skills.

6.2.3. TAIS I – Finland (UH)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: A balanced representation of service providers and beneficiaries (made of two distinct group, volunteers and asylum seekers).

The location of the issue: Mostly internal regarding the viability and content of the service, accessibility appears as external dimension.

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The nature/type of the success: Mostly process oriented, regarding communication, participation and interaction, as well as the easiness of joining and navigating in the programme. Increased knowledge and increased trust can be considered as outcome.

6.2.4. TAIS II – Finland (UH)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Slightly more emphasis on the beneficiaries: improvement in the quality of services, and better access. In case of service providers there is competence development, and an advocacy/lobby tool.

The location of the issue: Mostly internal: better and more diverse service, resulting in better reception conditions. Accessibility is the only (partially) external dimension.

The nature/type of the success: Mostly process oriented: enhanced services available. A remarkable result or impact-oriented success: the TAIS' data and documentation can be a tool for lobbying for funding for an enhanced reception service.

6.2.5. TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)

Level: Meso

Agency and ownership: Success is defined mostly from the perspective of the beneficiaries. The ARU appears as an important actor in the design and implementation of the TAIS. The participatory nature of the pilot is emphasized: *“The TAIS beneficiaries were active participants and the creators of the development process.”*

The location of the issue: Only internal factors, related to the content and process of the TAIS.

The nature/type of the success: Both process and outcome oriented: the participatory development and realisation of the TAIS itself, as well as the achieved competence development of the beneficiaries.

6.2.6. TAIS – Turkey (AU)

Level: Meso

Agency and ownership: A triangle of experts of the project team, trainers (direct service providers) and experts receiving training (local government service providers).

The location of the issue: Internal only: good communication and interaction between service providers and beneficiaries.

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The nature/type of the success: Process oriented, and outcome-related: competence development of both the beneficiaries and the service providers. Change in knowledge and attitudes regarding the concept of vulnerability. Interaction and communication between officials and vulnerable people.

6.2.7. TAIS – Jordan (YU)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Much more emphasis on the beneficiaries: their needs are the factors that determine the assessment. Service providers appear only in one dimension: the personality of the trainer contributed a lot to the success of the project.

The location of the issue: The internal dimension is the dominant one: the quality of the service, the development of the beneficiaries is in the focus, there is only one reference to the broader social and institutional environment: the prospective ability of beneficiaries to enrol in future university programmes.

The nature/type of the success: Mostly process oriented: the content of the training, the methods used, the relevance of the issues discussed. There is reference to the difficulty to measure actual results or impact, given the timeframe of the pilot.

6.2.8. TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Service providers' assessment dominate, though there is input from beneficiaries as well, and there is a conclusion given by the coordination team, and the ARU also appears.

The location of the issue: Both internal and external: gender awareness, and appropriate gender composition of the service providers; beneficiaries' engagement in the project; good cooperation with external partners; attention and support from the ARU. "Our ARU was definitely one of the success factors of the LIU TAIS in the area of Bekaa close to Syria."

The nature/type of the success: Process oriented elements: promoting accessibility and empowerment. Result oriented elements: beneficiaries' skills development, opening-up, self-realisation – even outside of the TAIS.

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6.3. A detailed summary of failures

6.3.1. TAIS – Spain (UCM)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: There is a balanced representation of beneficiaries, service providers and the project team (coordinators).

The location of the issue: The focus here is somewhat more on the external dimensions than on the internal ones. The context and expectations frame the failures: participants expected more (or other content), autonomy achieved through empowerment had an adverse effect on beneficiaries' interactions with other service providers. The pandemic was also mentioned as a hindering factor.

The nature/type of the failure: Failures are interpreted across the whole spectrum: there are process oriented ones (missed expectations about the focus), ones that link to outcomes (missed expectations about the goal), and ones that are about the result/impact (no evidence of better social integration perspectives).

6.3.2. TAIS – Italy (CESIE)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Problems related to beneficiaries as well as service providers are represented in a balanced way.

The location of the issue: A strong external factor was the ongoing pandemic that limited face-to-face interactions. Participants' social and economic problems as well as their level of Italian proficiency had an impact on the implementation as an internal factor. Sudden changes in the living conditions and circumstances of the participants can also be considered as an external factor.

The nature/type of the failure: Only process oriented issues were mentioned: reduction of the number of participants, altering the methodology and content of the programme.

6.3.3. TAIS I – Finland (UH)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Only the service providers' perspective is represented: limited outreach capacity, limited sustainability.

The location of the issue: Internal ones, problems stem from the actual design and capacity of the service.

The nature/type of the failure: Process-related: limited outreach and limited sustainability.

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6.3.4. TAIS II – Finland (UH)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Beneficiaries' perspective is stronger here: accessibility, targeting, and content-related issues are mentioned – there are mismatches between actual needs and services offered. The service providers perspective is represented by the lack of sustainability.

The location of the issue: The majority of the issues are internal, lack of external funding and the rapidly changing policy environment are mentioned as external ones.

The nature/type of the failure: Only process-related issues are mentioned: the content of the service, accessibility, and the lack of prospective funding.

6.3.5. TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)

Level: Meso

Agency and ownership: Problems related to beneficiaries as well as service providers are represented in a balanced way.

The location of the issue: Only the external dimension is mentioned: problems/failures are related to the lack of involvement of certain targeted beneficiaries due to existing political issues and conflicts. The effect of the pandemic as another external issue is discussed as well.

The nature/type of the failure: Process-related: changed focus and reduced activities compared to the initial plans. Outcome/output-related: reduced outreach of the project, less agencies involved as beneficiaries.

6.3.6. TAIS – Turkey (AU)

Level: Meso

Agency and ownership: There is a balanced representation of service providers and beneficiaries of the project.

The location of the issue: There is a strong internal factor regarding the beneficiaries: their negative attitudes and predispositions that were hard to influence. The Turkish society's generally negative attitude toward immigrants and tensions between the local population and newcomers is a closely related external dimension. And there is another strong external dimension affecting both service providers and beneficiaries: the social distancing measures due to the pandemic that resulted in online interactions that had a negative impact on the service.

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The nature/type of the failure: Process oriented: the limits of the online sessions. Result/impact oriented: the limited effect of the training on beneficiaries' attitudes.

6.3.7. TAIS – Jordan (YU)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Mostly technical issues are mentioned that affect beneficiaries and service providers alike. Needs and expectations of beneficiaries are reflected more strongly.

The location of the issue: Only internal issues are mentioned: training methodology, the physical and infrastructural environment, design and administration.

The nature/type of the failure: Only process oriented issues are mentioned.

6.3.8. TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)

Level: Micro

Agency and ownership: Beneficiaries, service providers and the coordination team appear in a balanced representation.

The location of the issue: There is a dynamic relationship between internal factors influenced by external ones. The main issue here is the level of responsiveness and adaptability on behalf of the coordination team and the level of motivation and autonomy of the beneficiaries – all determined/influenced by the political, economic and social crises that emerged in Lebanon before and during the TAIS implementation.

The nature/type of the failure: The process-oriented dimension is the dominant one: better assessment, better planning, and more flexible implementation could have improved the TAIS.

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6.4. Successes and failures: concluding remarks

6.4.1. Successes

Regarding actors, 5 reports mention beneficiaries and service providers only, and 3 reports include the perspective of the coordination team as well. 5 of the 8 reports put a much greater emphasis on the perspective of the beneficiaries. 2 reports mention the role and contribution of the ARU to the TAIS' success.

As for the location of the success, internal factors dominate: 2 reports mention only internal ones, in 4 out of the other 6 that mention both external and internal ones, the internal ones are discussed in much more details.

The successes mentioned are mostly process-related. There are much less output/outcome related issues mentioned and impact related ones are only occasionally. 7 report mention one or more process-related successes, 4 mention output-related ones, and 3 mentions result or impact-related ones.

6.4.2. Failures

Regarding actors, 5 reports mention beneficiaries and service providers only, and 2 reports include the perspective of the coordination team as well. There is 1 report that mention only the service providers. The ARU is not mentioned in the context of failures. The greater emphasis on the perspective of the beneficiaries that characterised the success reports is not apparent here: only 2 reports discuss more from the beneficiaries' perspective.

As for the location of the success, there is a more diverse landscape than in case of successes: 2 reports mention only internal ones, 1 report only external ones, and 5 mention both types. 2 out of these 5 emphasize on external ones and 1 tilts toward the internal ones. And there is one that describes a dynamic and interlinking relationship between the internal and external ones.

The failures mentioned are even more process-related than in case of the successes. Output/outcome and impact related issues are mentioned only occasionally. All 8 report mention one or more process-related failures (5 of them only these), 2 mention output-related ones, and 2 mentions result or impact-related ones.

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7. Appendix. TAIS co-designers: Stakeholders and beneficiaries

The following tables provide an overview of each TAIS, including ARU members, material outcomes, the number of beneficiaries and stakeholders according to their gender.

7.1. TAIS – Spain (UCM)

TAIS – Spain (UCM)	
Short title of TAIS	Entrepreneurship training and education
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nantik Lum 2. Proyecto Esperanza-Adoratrices 3. Paz.ai 4. Speak Madrid 5. Take a chef 6. Universidad de León 7. Universidad Complutense 8. Red REAS 9. Coperama (COCETA) 10. Cámara de Comercio de Madrid 11. Psicología sin Fronteras 12. Red Acoge 13. CONSENS 14. Ashoka 15. Asociación Madrid Empleo y Desarrollo (AMED) 16. Ayuntamiento de Alcobendas 17. Ayuntamiento de Madrid 18. CEAR 19. Fundación Merced Migraciones 20. KifKif 21. La Rueda 22. Fundación Recover Hospitales para África 23. San Ricardo Pampuri 24. Compluemprende
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	1 June 2020 – 30 November 2020
Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	1 December 2020 – 30 April 2021

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TAIS – Spain (UCM)	
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	1 May 2021 – 30 November 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	20	23
	Male	3	
Number of vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS:	Female	14	14
	Male	0	
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	0
	Male	0	
			37

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7.2. TAIS – Italy (CESIE)

TAIS – Italy (CESIE)	
Short title of TAIS	ALL you can LEARN
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CSC Centro per lo Sviluppo Creativo ‘Danilo Dolci’ 2. IKENGA, migrant association for socio-cultural promotion; 3. CLEDU, Legal Clinic for Human Rights of the University of Palermo; 4. ARCI Porco Rosso, Sportello Sans-Papiers; 5. CPIA, Regional School Office for Sicily. Provincial Centre for Adult Education; 6. Istituto Don Calabria (Vulnerable group housing); 7. ASP, Provincial Health Care System: Ethno-psychology Service; Voluntary legal guardian for unaccompanied minor; 8. INTEGRA NETWORK (30+ members: connecting residential care providers, educators, successful care leavers, VET providers, educational institutions, local authorities working with migrants, guardians of un-accompanied minors). 9. Emergency Reception Centres: CasPa 4 San Francesco 10. Associazione Casa Famiglia Nostra Signora di Lourdes – Onlus (sheltered home for people living with a disability) 11. Centro Astalli – Jesuit Refugee Service (voluntary association) 12. Il Pellegrino della Terra, Human Trafficking Victims support centre 13. Donne di Benin City – Human Trafficking Victims support centre 14. Donne Islamiche Fatima 15. Cooperativa Nuova Generazione (CNG) (CAS Musciotto, Progetto Freedom) 16. Società Cooperativa Sociale 3P Padre Pino Puglisi (CAS S.Francesco) 17. <u>Consorzio</u> “Umana Solidarietà s.c.s. (CAS Borgo) 18. Multivolti (Social Enterprise) 19. Associazione CU.CI.RE (Cooperative Union for Creative Ideas and Re-starting Entrepreneurship)
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	1 April 2020 – 30 September 2020

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Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	1 September 2020 – 30 April 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	1 May 2021 – 31 October 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	6	9
	Male	3	
Number of vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS:	Female	27	27
	Male	0	
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	102	149
	Male	47	
			185

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7.3. TAIS I – Finland (UH)

TAIS I - Finland (UH)	
Short title of TAIS	Multilingual online forum
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. University of Helsinki 2. The Finnish Red Cross professionals 3. Individual citizens (FDPs and volunteers)
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	18 May 2020 – 12 August 2020
Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	7 January 2021 – 17 February 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	21 September 2021 – 1 November 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	14	21
	Male	5	
Number of vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS:	Female	0	27
	Male	27	
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	4
	Male	4	
			52

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7.4. TAIS II – Finland (UH)

TAIS II – Finland (UH)	
Short title of TAIS	Development of child-care services in Finnish reception centres
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	1. The Finnish Red Cross
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	Execution: 1 July 2020 – 30 September 2020 Process evaluation: 1 September 2020 – 31 October 2020
Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	Execution: 1 November 2020 – 31 January 2021 Process evaluation: 1 February 2021 – 31 March 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	Execution: 1 November 2021 – 31 December 2021 Outcome evaluation: 1 December 2021 – 31 December 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	Female	Male	
TAIS implementation team	Female	9	12
	Male	3	
Number of vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS:	Asylum-seeking families with children		28
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	0
	Male	0	
			40

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7.5. TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)

TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)	
Short title of TAIS	Trajectory monitoring toolbox for social workers working with refugees
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	<p>RAISD consortium member and leading actor of TAIS implementation: Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants</p> <p>ARU members and invited participants of ARU meetings are affiliated with the following institutions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. UNHCR (international organization) 2. IOM (international organization) 3. Terre des Hommes Foundation (international NGO) 4. Amnesty International (international NGO) 5. Directorate General of Aliens Policing (national policy maker) 6. Family Support Centre - Budapest XIV (local policy maker) 7. Family Support Centre - Győr (local policy maker) 8. Károlyi István Centre for unaccompanied minors (local policy maker) 9. Hungarian Helsinki Committee (NGO) 10. Hungarian Baptist Aid (NGO) 11. Cordelia Foundation (NGO) 12. Diaconia of the Lutheran Church (NGO) 13. Hungarian Evangelical Brotherhood (NGO) 14. Jesuit Refugee Service (NGO) 15. Next Step EU (NGO) 16. She 4 She (NGO) 17. Subjective Values Foundation (NGO) 18. Artemisszió Foundation (NGO) 19. Oltalom Caritative Association (NGO) 20. Oltalom Sports Association (NGO) 21. Ferencváros Community Foundation (NGO) 22. Eötvös Loránd University (academia)
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	15 May 2020 – 15 November 2020

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TAIS – Hungary (Menedék)	
Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	15 November 2020 – 15 April 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	15 April 2021 – 15 November 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	5	8
	Male	2	
Social workers and professionals involved in the analysis	Female	8	10
	Male	2	
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	21	34
	Male	13	
			54

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7.6. TAIS – Turkey (AU)

TAIS – Turkey (AU)	
Short title of TAIS	Accessing and Participating in Basic Daily Life Practices through Monitoring
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality 2. Tepebaşı Municipality 3. ESGİAD 4. Sedef Medya 5. 19 Mayıs University 6. Ülkü Primary School 7. WGSS 8. Ministry of Health 9. Eskişehir Bar Association 10. Forcible Displaced People 11. TALDANS Art Collective
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	1 June 2020 – 15 March 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	16 March 2021 – 15 August 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	16 August 2021 – 31 December 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
	TAIS implementation team	Female	
	Male	6	
Number of vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS:	Female	2	3
	Male	1	
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	37	43
	Male	6	
			58

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7.7. TAIS – Jordan (YU)

TAIS – Jordan (YU)	
Short title of TAIS	Psychological Refugee Support Forum (PRSF)
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Karmah for Training and Logistic Services and Educational consulting [4] 2. AL-KETAB & AL-SONNA ASSOCIATION [2] 3. North Association for Sustainable Development [2] 4. Alfarouq society [2] 5. Ministry of health [2] 6. Irbid governance [2] 7. Nawafeth for Training and Sustainable Development [2] 8. Justice center for legal aid [2] 9. Freelancers [10] 10. Refugees [2] <p>Most of ARUs assign the MOU personally not by their organizations, so not all of the above signed it.</p>
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	1 May 2020 – 31 October 2020
Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	1 November 2020 – 30 April 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	1 May 2021 – 31 December 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	2	8
	Male	6	
Number of vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS:	Female	42	57
	Male	15	
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	25	40
	Male	15	
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7.8. TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)

TAIS – Lebanon (LIU)	
Short title of TAIS	Health 4 SEAD “Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development”
Name of associated organisations, institutions (ARU members):	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SPARK-NGO 2. Tatweer Baldna-NGO 3. UNRWA Palestinian Educational Establishment 4. LIU Health Committees 5. Ex Minister of Foreign Trade in Lebanon
Implementation piloting ROUND 1:	1 April 2020 – 31 July 2020
Implementation piloting ROUND 2:	1 November 2020 – 15 July 2021
Implementation piloting ROUND 3:	16 July 2021 – 30 September 2021

Stakeholders and beneficiaries	Gender division		Total
TAIS implementation team	Female	4	10
	Male	6	
Number of vulnerable individuals directly benefitting from the TAIS:	Female	18	32
	Male	14	
Number of other beneficiaries (service providers, professionals, public employees, NGO workers etc. benefitting from the TAIS)	Female	0	0
	Male	0	
			42

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